

EXPLANATION OF THE ISSUE OF THE ORIENTATION OF VALUES IN THE WORKS OF EASTERN SCIENTISTS

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Abstract. In the article, the opinions of the encyclopedic scientists of the East about the spirituality of the person, the direction of values and moral perfection are put forward. In particular, we can see that one of the main criteria for the development of human perfection of Eastern scholars is its spiritual and moral value system.

Key words: personality, moral views, education, training, personal development, community, morality, value, spirituality, good, bad, endurance, humility.

Аннотация. В статье изложены мнения ученых-энциклопедистов Востока о духовности человека, ценностном направлении и нравственной зрелости. В частности, мы видим, что одним из главных критериев развития человеческого совершенства у восточных ученых является его духовно-нравственная система ценностей.

Ключевые слова: личность, нравственные взгляды, воспитание, воспитание, личностное развитие, сообщество, мораль, ценность, духовность, добро, зло, выносливость, смирение.

Аннотация. Мақолада Шарқнинг қомусий олимлари томонидан илгари сурилган шахс маънавияти, қадриятлар йўналганлиги ҳамда ахлоқий камолоти борасидаги фикрлар илгари сурилган. Айниқса, Шарқ алломаларининг инсон камолотига етишининг асосий мезонларидан бири бу унинг маънавий-ахлоқий қадриятлар тизими эканлигини кўришимиз мумкин.

Калит сўзлар: шахс, ахлоқий қарашлар, таълим, тарбия, шахс камолоти, жамоа, ахлоқ, қадрият, маънавият, яхшилик, ёмонлик, чидамлилиқ, камтарлик.

The encyclopedic scientists of the East give a number of opinions about education and personal development. For example, in the works of our scholars such as Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Yusuf Khos Khajib, Abdurrahman Jami, Jalaluddin Davani, the mechanisms that ensure the perfection of a person are described in detail. In particular, the environment, human community, and interpersonal relations are the main factors influencing the development of a person. From this point of view, the life values of a person are determined by the fact that he has a unique place in the life of society, the development of such

processes as self-awareness, self-evaluation, self-control. . It should be said that the encyclopedic scientists of the East know that personal development is not a process that appears by itself, but has a complementary importance.

As it is known, Abu Nasr Farabi, a person cannot reach maturity alone. He believes that he needs to be in contact with others, their help or relationships.

Abu Nasr Farabi says that this can be achieved through proper education. Because education carried out in accordance with the purpose makes a person mature both intellectually and morally, in particular, he treats human nature and the laws of society correctly, observes the rules of order of society.

According to Abu Nasr Farbi, morality should be the most important quality of a person. This quality does not develop suddenly. It is formed in the process of human interaction, social environment, and development of society.

He says that morality is manifested and formed as a result of the struggle between good and evil. Goodness and badness are used as criteria for determining human behavior.

He includes good qualities such as correctness, justice, self-control, honesty, humility, grace, steadfastness, prudence, generosity, sweetness, fairness in leadership.

Evil vices include envy, greed, unhealthy competition, self-interest, careerism, and greed.

Therefore, Abu Rayhan Beruni divides all the moral qualities of the spiritual image of a person into two types, such as good and bad. This is one of the important aspects of moral concepts and moral integrity in accordance with the development of ideas created by mankind [2].

Abu Ali Ibn Sina also analyzes the important moral aspects of human perfection and defines each of them. For example, he shows justice as the main criterion of spiritual life. A person acquires justice with contentment, courage, and wisdom, refrains from bad vices, strengthens goodness, and gets real spiritual pleasure, says the scientist. The positive moral qualities of a person include generosity, endurance, humility, love, moderation, intelligence, prudence, perseverance, loyalty, shyness, performance and others.

It introduces contentment and moderation into the emotional power of a person, endurance, intelligence into the power of anger, wisdom into the power of anger, prudence into intelligence, loyalty, shyness, performance, pity, honesty into the power of difference.

The scientist considers contentment as one of the emotional qualities and says that if a person refrains from greed, observes moderation, overcomes the

manifestation of greed, a person should consciously use his capabilities to overcome bad vices.

Abu Ali Ibn Sina also includes the high moral qualities of people being friends with each other, living and cooperating. Because everyone, while living with people in society, strives to live with them in a friendly way.

According to Abu Ali Ibn Sinoni, no matter how mature a person is mentally and physically, if his knowledge and strength do not correspond to moral standards, such a person cannot be considered a true member of society and he cannot benefit society. Ibn Sina considered people who strive to live for the common good of the people and not just for themselves to be good moral people.

Yusuf Xos Xojib yurtni idora etuvchi va xalqni boshqaruvchilarini ikki toifaga bo'lib, birinchisi adolatli siyosatni yurituvchi beklar va ikkinchisi dono olimlar deydi. Chunki siyosatchilar yurtni boshqarsa, olimlar ma'rifiy yo'l-yo'riq ko'rsatadi.

Olim bilimni ziyoga, tengi yo'q javohirga o'xshatib, u insonni yuksaltiradi, jahonning sir-asrorini bilib olishiga yordam beradi deydi. Insoniyat nimaga erishgan bo'lsa bilim tufayli erishganligini ta'kidlaydi. Ammo bu boylukni hech kim o'g'irlay olmaydi deb bilim va zakovatni muqaddas do'st mehribon qarindosh, kiyim va oziq sifatida ta'riflaydi.

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Yusuf Khos Khajib considers another and most important aspect of human development to be moral development. From the content of "Kutadgu Bilig", we can note that it is a work of advice, instruction, education, morals and manners, intelligence and wisdom. The thinker illuminates his moral views, that is, social relations, moral relations between all classes of society, based on practice. These principles of moral behavior, requirements and tasks are expressed on the basis of mutual discussions of heroes throughout the century. It describes the interaction, morals, and treatment requirements of social groups of all classes and categories. It distinguishes the characteristics, habits, qualifications and skills of various professions.

Kaikovus says that it is better for a person to be without a brother than without a friend. The more friends a person has, the more his faults are hidden, and his virtues increase. emphasizes. Also, knowing how to distinguish between a friend and an enemy, he advised not to show oneself as weak in front of the enemy, to avoid a strong enemy and a friend who is a traitor, a slanderer, and a friend who reveals secrets. He emphasizes that every person should have the following qualities. These are not to fight with someone superior to oneself, not to sit in the middle of the congregation with an envious person, not to argue with an ignorant person, not to be friends with a hypocrite, not to be friends with a hypocrite, not to deal with a liar, not to deal with a miser not to be in a conversation, not to sit in the same place with an enemy, not to tell secrets to people, to try to remove that fault if someone tells you about your fault, not to praise someone too much or flatter someone too much, to take care of someone who is in need, to be forgiving to be, to be kind to the little ones, not to order the same work to two people are life recommendations [3].

Along with other encyclopedic scholars of the East, Omar Khayyam also believed that qualities in human behavior are formed gradually. He states that if a person does not have any positive moral qualities, he should try to create them in himself, and get rid of bad vices by his own will.

According to Omar Khayyam, behavior occurs in two ways: through habituation and in the process of thinking.

Umar Khayyam stated that the goal of education should be "to form a person with a sound mind, a sharp mind and a sharp intellect." can achieve inspiration and with its help create a high level of intelligence". But that alone is not enough, a person must love his loved ones in order to have high morals.

Omar Khayyam's excessive demands on himself and people were expressed in the rules he developed about the need to educate a person from childhood and throughout his life. According to Omar Khayyam, a person who combines knowledge of science, behavior and determination to do good to all people is such a perfect person in terms of all practical and theoretical qualities.

In Alisher Navoi's imagination, creativity, ability, and love of science are the highest qualities characteristic of a perfect person. Because he wanted a happy life. According to Navoi, a wise person with intellectual abilities believes in his strength and intelligence. That's why Alisher Navoi, explaining the importance of science, describes science as a light that illuminates the darkness, a lamp, a sun that illuminates the path of life, a factor that shows the true image of people

In the works of Alisher Navoi, methods and methods of educating a perfect person are also expressed. In the works of Alisher Navoi, it is recommended to deal with child education in the family and at school, and use the model method. Education and training should be carried out by parents and teachers.

According to Alisher Navoi, a perfect person is intellectually, morally, intellectually, creatively talented, knowledgeable, intelligent and wise, honest, humanitarian, generous, patient, just, kind, humble, healthy and physically strong, brave and brave.

He attaches great importance to the upbringing of the child and his formation as a person, characterizing that the child is the "light" of the house, the child brings happiness and happiness to the family [4].

From the above points, it can be seen that in the researches of encyclopedic scientists of the East, a person's views on life, relationships, and life goals were studied in a wide range. At this point, it can be said that a person's realization of life goals, determination of stable relationships with life, and understanding of the value of life are related to their personal qualities.

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